

Assessing the impact of data entry, wrong testimonies and misinterpretation errors in missing person searches

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Abstract

Criminal investigations often rely on the use of physical traits to search for the potential person of interest. When DNA data are not available, this information is key. Physical trait data are collected from victim testimonies, obtained from video cameras, or photos surrounding the crime scene, among others. These data are used to search across databases to define potential persons of interest to be further analyzed. Despite its crucial relevance, only a few approaches mathematically formalize the physical trait evidence, providing tools for computing the statistical weight. Recently, some models have been developed that allow computing likelihood ratios, while accounting for potential data entry errors, typos, misinterpretation, among other phenomena that could hamper the search. Here, we exhaustively explore the impact of the error parameters in those models, providing a clear idea of how these errors can affect the search.

Keywords: Likelihood Ratio, Forensic Science, Missing Person, Statistical weight of evidence

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1. Introduction

In forensic investigations, the use of physical traits plays a pivotal role in the identification of potential persons of interest, particularly when DNA evidence is not available [1], [2]. Moreover, the incorporation of nongenetic data has been proposed to be useful when DNA is not sufficient to achieve conclusive results. This is common in cases where the statistical power of DNA evidence is poor, mainly due to damaged samples or a few distant relatives of the person to be identified [3], [4].

Physical trait data, which can be collected from various sources, such as victim testimony, video surveillance, and photographs of the crime scene, serves as the primary means of narrowing down suspects in many criminal investigations [5]. This information is typically used to search databases, in order to match individuals who fit the description provided [6], [7]. However, inherent subjectivity and potential inaccuracies in the collection and interpretation of these data pose significant challenges. Errors in data entry, incorrect testimonies, and misinterpretations of physical characteristics can severely compromise the reliability of such searches, potentially leading to false positives or missed identifications [8].

The importance of addressing these errors has been underscored in the forensic literature [8], [9]. Early efforts to incorporate physical traits into criminal investigations were heavily based on exact matching criteria, which failed to account for common issues such as typographical errors, incorrect testimonies, or subjective misinterpretation of traits such as height, hair color, or distinguishing marks.

In forensic science, the concept of statistical weight of evidence is a keystone [10]. This aspect is widely covered in DNA evidence, where it is assessed using a likelihood ratio (LR) approach that summarizes the likelihood of competing hypotheses in order to interpret the genetic data. Several approaches have been developed to compute these LRs [11]–[13]. Specifically, in missing person and disaster victim identifications, competing hypotheses are: H_1 : The unidentified person (UP) is the missing person (MP), and H_2 : UP is not related to MP.

Recent advances have focused on developing mathematical models that improve the robustness of search based on physical characteristics [8]. These models introduce probabilistic frameworks that allow the computation of LRs while accounting for potential errors in the data. By incorporating these error parameters, these models aim to provide a more nuanced assessment of the evidence, improving the accuracy and reliability of searches when DNA data are unavailable.

Despite the development of these models, there remains a gap in the comprehensive understanding of how specific types of errors, such as data entry errors, erroneous testimonies, and misinterpretation, affect the results of missing person searches. Studies have shown that such errors can dramatically influence the results of a search, either by increasing the likelihood of false identifications or by failing to identify a match altogether [8], [9]. Forensic professionals are therefore in need of tools that allow them to assess the impact of these errors and make informed decisions during investigations.

In this study, our aim is to fill this gap by exhaustively analyzing the impact of various error parameters on physical trait-based searches. We examine the influence of data entry errors, incorrect testimonies, and misinterpretation errors on the computation of LRs and the overall success of the search process. By simulating a wide range of scenarios, we provide forensic investigators with a clearer understanding of how these errors affect search reliability and offer guidance on adjusting search parameters to mitigate their impact. Our findings are expected to provide valuable insight for practitioners, helping them to better manage the uncertainties inherent in trait-based searches and ultimately enhancing the robustness of missing person investigations where DNA evidence is unavailable.

2. Methods

The purpose of this study was to evaluate how varying error rates impact the expected likelihood ratio (LR) under two hypotheses: H_1 (the unidentified person, UP, is the missing person, MP) and H_2 (the UP is not the MP). To achieve this, we used the *mispitools* package [14] and developed custom scripts to iteratively adjust the error rates that affect the assignment of age and hair color in the identification process. Specifically, for the H_1 scenario, we simulated 10,000 cases in which the MP was a 40-year-old woman with brown hair. The age error range was varied to assess the impact of incorrect age estimation, while an equal error range was applied to hair color assignment, allowing misclassification between predefined hair color categories. This step was critical in observing how the LR responds to uncertainties in the real world in non-genetic variables.

The simulations iteratively adjusted the error rates in these two key variables (age, sex and hair color). For each iteration, we recalculated the LR for both H_1 and H_2 , evaluating the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for each case. This approach has been proven to be consistent in evaluating the statistical power in DNA-based identifications [15]. Under H_1 , the assumption was that the UP is the MP, and thus we expected

a higher LR when the errors were minimal. Conversely, under H2, where the UP is not the MP, we expected a lower LR, although not necessarily zero, due to the inclusion of error rates in the model. The iterative process allowed us to explore how error ranges, specifically for age estimation and hair color assignment, altered the LR and its ability to distinguish between H1 and H2. All simulations were conducted using *misptools*, which allowed us to efficiently compute $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ values across a wide range of error conditions, providing robust results for both hypotheses.

Data used for the preliminary investigation and identification process come from multiple sources, including legal documentation, relatives and witnesses' testimony, social media information, and direct observation. *Misptools* provides a set of function for simulating preliminary investigation data emulating real-world scenarios. In this study, we focus on three key variables: hair color (C), biological sex (S), and age (A). Hair color was treated as a polytomous categorical variable with five possible values: brown (1), black (2), blond (3), auburn (4) and red (5). Biological sex was dichotomous, with female (F) and male (M) as possible values, while age was treated as a continuous variable ranging from 0 to 100. These variables were organized into databases for both UPs and MPs. All these characteristics form the phenotype, which is used to compare UPs with MPs in the identification process.

The database matching process used in this study was based on LR models previously developed [8]. Historically, the data from the MPs were gathered from interviews, legal sources and direct observation and compared to a UP database (Figure 1). Previous approaches involved filtering cases based on exact matches, correctly identifying some while erroneously discarding others due to typographical or classification errors. These early models lacked a robust method for incorporating these errors, which often resulted in an LR of zero, and erroneous exclusions, when mismatches occurred. The newer LR models, as used in this study, incorporate error probabilities, allowing the possibility of identifying a match even when there are errors in age or hair color. The methodology explored how the expected LR for H1 and H2 varies when different error rates are introduced, ensuring that errors do not automatically lead to LR values of zero, thus providing a more accurate representation of real-world uncertainties in identification.

Figure 1. Diagram illustrating the data comparison process in missing person identification. Suspect or MP characteristics, such as pigmentation (hair color), biological sex, and age, are compared against a database of unidentified persons containing the same attributes. The comparison can lead to three possible outcomes: an accurate match, an accurate mismatch, or a wrong classification due to errors such as data entry mistakes or typographical errors. These errors can result in misclassification, where a true match may be overlooked or an incorrect match could be made.

3. Results

In this section, we present the impact of varying error rates in non-genetic variables, biological sex, hair color, and age, on the expected LR under both hypotheses: H1 and H2. The results are displayed in

a series of figures, each highlighting the sensitivity of the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ to changes in the error rates for each variable. The error rates are indicated as ϵ_S for biological sex, ϵ_C for hair color, and ϵ_A for age. All simulations involved 10,000 iterations for each scenario. Figure 2 shows the effect of varying the error rate in biological sex assignment (ϵ_S) on the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$. The left panel illustrates the behavior of $E[\log_{10}(\text{LR})|H1]$, where increasing the error in biological sex leads to a gradual decrease in the expected LR. This indicates that higher levels of uncertainty in biological sex reduce the likelihood of correctly identifying UP as MP. In the right panel, the expected negative $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H2, $E[\log_{10}(\text{LR})|H2]$, also decreases as the error in the sex classification increases, showing that as errors grow, it becomes harder to exclude incorrect matches. These results confirm that even minor misclassifications in biological sex can significantly influence the LR for both hypotheses.

Figure 2. Expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ under varying error rates in the biological sex classification for H1 (UP is MP) and H2 (UP is not MP). The left panel shows the decrease in the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H1 as the error in biological sex increases, indicating that the likelihood of correctly identifying UP as MP diminishes with higher error rates. The right panel shows the corresponding decrease in the negative expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H2, reflecting that, even when UP is not MP, classification errors in biological sex reduce the certainty of ruling out the match. These results demonstrate how errors in biological sex classification affect the strength of the LR under both hypotheses.

Figure 3 focuses on the effect of errors in hair color assignment (ϵ_C). Similarly to the results for biological sex, the left panel shows that the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H1 decreases as ϵ_C increases. The right panel demonstrates that the negative expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H2 also decreases as the error in hair color increases. This suggests that misclassifications in hair color, even when small, can affect the LR by reducing both the ability to confirm a match and to reject nonmatching UPs. Given that hair color is a polytomous categorical variable with five potential categories (brown, black, blond, auburn, and red), the results underscore the sensitivity of the LR to classification errors in this trait.

Figure 3. Expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ under varying error rates in hair color classification for H1 (UP is MP) and H2 (UP is not MP). The left panel shows the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H1 decreasing as the error in hair color increases, indicating that higher error rates in hair color classification reduce the likelihood of correctly identifying UP as MP. The right panel illustrates the corresponding decrease in the negative expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H2, showing that as hair color errors increase, the certainty in excluding a match between UP and MP decreases. These curves highlight the sensitivity of the LR to errors in non-genetic traits like hair color under both hypotheses.

Figure 4 examines the impact of varying the age estimation errors (ϵ_A) on the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ under both hypotheses. The left panel

displays the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H1, where the LR decreases as the error in age estimation increases. This trend highlights the critical role that accurate age estimation plays in correctly identifying UP as MP. In the right panel, the negative expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H2 declines similarly as the age error increases, showing that as uncertainty in age estimation increases, the ability to exclude incorrect matches weakens.

Figure 4. Expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ under varying error rates in age estimation for H1 (UP is MP) and H2 (UP is not MP). The left panel displays the expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H1, where the likelihood of correctly identifying UP as MP decreases as the error in age estimation increases. The right panel shows the corresponding decrease in the negative expected $\log_{10}(\text{LR})$ for H2, demonstrating that as age estimation errors grow, the certainty in excluding a match between UP and MP diminishes. These results underscore the critical role that accurate age estimation plays in influencing the LR under both hypotheses.

These results demonstrate the impact that error rates in nongenetic variables can have on the LR in missing person identification cases. Errors in biological sex, hair color, and age reduce the strength of the LR, increasing uncertainty under both H1 and H2. The use of likelihood ratio models that account for these errors ensures that nonzero LR values can still be obtained even when typographical or observational errors occur, improving the robustness of the identification process.

4. Conclusions

This study highlights the significant impact of error rates in nongenetic variables, biological sex, hair color, and age, on the likelihood ratio (LR) used in missing person identification. Our results demonstrate that even small misclassifications or uncertainties in these variables can substantially reduce the strength of the LR under both hypotheses, H1 (UP is MP) and H2 (UP is not MP). As error rates increase, the ability to correctly identify or exclude matches decreases, underscoring the importance of minimizing these uncertainties in real-world cases. The reduction of the strength of the evidence when errors are incorporated to the model explicitly allows to correct over confidence in the data.

The use of LR models that explicitly account for such errors is crucial in ensuring robust and reliable identification outcomes. These models allow for the inclusion of typographical or observational errors without automatically resulting in LR values of zero, which could incorrectly dismiss potential matches. By incorporating error probabilities, the models improve the reliability of identification processes, even in the presence of imperfect data. This approach ensures that identification efforts remain resilient to the inherent uncertainties of nongenetic variables, improving the overall effectiveness of missing person investigations.

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